

TEMPERATURE AND PRESSURE INFLUENCES IN INFILTRATION RATE DURING FABRICATING FIBER CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE VIA PRECURSOR IMPREGNATION PYROLYSIS

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SUMMARY: The present paper studies an infiltration processing of fabricating Fiber Reinforced Ceramic Matrix Composites via precursor impregnation pyrolysis method. Temperature and pressure's influences on infiltration procedure are emphatically discussed. The optimum infiltration temperature and pressure of polycarbosilane/Divinyl Benzene solution and the melted PCS are 50~60 °C and 2MPa, and are 300 °C and 2MPa, respectively.

KEYWORDS: Infiltration processing, Ceramic Matrix Composite, Precursor impregnation pyrolysis, Polycarbosilane, Temperature, Pressure

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforcement has been employed for toughening ceramics so that the ceramics toughened can exhibit non-brittle mechanical behavior (although all its constituents are intrinsically brittle), and can also enhance their strength, thermal stability and impact resistance [1-5]. Therefore, much attention has been paid on the researches about Fiber Reinforced Ceramic Matrix Composites (FRCMC). Every advanced technical country all takes FRCMC fabrications to be an advanced technique. Several processing techniques have been employed for fabricating FRCMC[6-8], for example, Hot Pressing (HP), Reaction Bonding (RB), Direction Melted Oxide (DMO), Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI), Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD), Sol-gel, Precursor Impregnation Pyrolysis (PIP). From cost-effectiveness considerations, the PIP, especially, adopting three-dimensional (3D) woven fiber performs to reinforce ceramic matrix, is considered as an effective and advanced method to fabricate FRCMC because of the outstanding advantages such as simple processing, lower pyrolysis temperature, short fabrication cycles (in comparison with CVI/CVD process). And it can also profit by the processes of fabricating Fiber Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites (FRPMC) and the carbon-carbon (C/C) composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Raw materials

A polymer precursor used to prepare silicon carbide (SiC) ceramic in FRCMC is polycarbosilane (PCS) supplied by National University of Defense Technology (UNDT). Its molecular weight is 1500 and soft point is 217-227 . The fiber reinforcement used in this paper is 3D PAN-based carbon fiber (Made in Jilin Carbon Co.) woven preforms, the strength of its carbon fiber is more than 4000MPa and its stiffness is more than 200GPa. The 3D preforms are woven to an unbalanced weave design with high fiber volume fractions in one or two directions.

Infiltration processing of the composites

The Infiltration processing of the composites can be described as follows: first, the 3D carbon fiber woven preforms are tailored, in which the carbon fiber must be treated with actone in order to remove any surface finishes. Second, the PCS/DVB solution system of which PCS is dissolved in divinyl benzene (DVB) previously prepared or melted PCS system is impregnated (via vacuum) into the interstices of the preforms, respectively. Finally, the systems above mentioned are heated from room temperature (RT) to some temperatures (less 120 for PCS/DVB system, high than 220 for melted PCS system) under pressure applied (by Nitrogen atmosphere) to allow the PCS/DVB solution or melted PCS to flow into the network pockets of the preform.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Influence of temperatures on PCS/DVB solution viscosity

The viscosity of the precursor PCS/DVB(1:0.4wt%) solution at different temperatures are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Viscosity of the PCS/DVB solution at different temperatures

Temperature ()	20	40	60	80
Viscosity (mPa.s)	19444	3131	1061	194

Fig. 1 gives the experimental curves of the PCS/DVB solution viscosity versus temperatures. From Fig.1, it can be seen that the PCS/DVB solution viscosity descends when the temperature is raised. In lower temperature zone, from RT to 40 , the PCS/DVB solution viscosity decrease tendency is very obvious, however, the viscosity change begins to have a flat tendency from 40 , and the viscosity descends very slowly above 60 .

Fig. 1: PCS/DVB solution viscosity versus temperatures

Infiltration rate for the PCS/DVB solution system

The influences of temperatures and pressures on the infiltration rate for PCS/DVB system (1:0.4wt%) are shown in Table 2. The experimental infiltration rate curves versus temperatures in different pressures for the solution are shown in Fig 2.

Table 2: Influences of temperature and pressure on the infiltration rate for PCS/DVB system

Pressure (MPa)	2	2	2	10	10	10
Temperature ()	RT.	50~60	100	RT	50~60	100
Infiltration rate (%)	44.7	51.9	40.3	46.5	44.2	40.8

Fig 2: Infiltration rate versus temperature in different pressures for PCS/DVB system

From Table 2 and Fig. 2, for 2MPa pressure, the infiltration rate for PCS/DVB solution increases firstly and then descends when temperature is raised, it can be at a peak when temperature is 50~60 .The PCS/DVB solution viscosity is rather large at RT, its mobility is bad, so that the infiltration rate for PCS/DVB solution is rather low. When temperature is raised to 50~60 , the PCS/DVB solution viscosity quickly lowers, its mobility becomes good, so, it can infiltrate into 3D carbon fiber woven preforms easily, and its infiltration rate is higher. But when temperature is raised to 100 , the PCS/DVB solution viscosity is too low, its infiltration rate is even lower than that at RT. At 10MPa pressure, the PCS/DVB solution infiltration rate descends when temperature is raised, because its mobility is good and can easily infiltrate into 3D carbon fiber woven preforms. But when temperature is raised , the PCS/DVB solution viscosity is too low to maintain the infiltration rate at RT, when pressure is elevated, the mobility of PCS/DVB solution can be enhanced , it is beneficial to improve infiltration rate. At 50~60 , when pressure is elevated, the infiltration rate descends. At 100 , the pressure only has a slight effect on infiltration rate.

The infiltrating process conditions of fabricating FRCMC via PCS/DVB solution precursor impregnation pyrolysis method can be described as follows: infiltration temperature and pressure of PCS/DVB solution are 50~60 and 2MPa, respectively.

Infiltration rate for the melted PCS system

The influences of temperatures and pressures on the infiltration rate for the melted PCS system are shown in Table 3. The experimental curves of the infiltration rate for melted PCS versus pressures at different temperatures are shown in Fig. 3.

Table 3: Influences of temperature and pressure on the infiltration rate for melted PCS system

Pressure (MPa)	2	5	10	2	5	10
Temperature ()	250	250	250	300	300	300
Infiltration rate (%)	13.7	16.6	36.6	46.6	33.1	18.7

Fig. 3: Infiltration rate versus pressure at different temperatures for the melted PCS system

From Table 3 and Fig.3, at 250 °C, the infiltration rate for the melted PCS system will be enhanced when pressure is raised. Because the molecular weight of PCS adopted in the present research is 1500 and soft point is 217-227 °C, its mobility is bad at 250 °C, so pressure elevating is in favor of the infiltrating of the melted PCS system. But, at 300 °C, the infiltration rate for the melted PCS system lowers when pressure is raised. From Fig. 3, it can be also seen that the infiltration rate for the melted PCS system can be enhanced when temperature is raised at lower pressure. But temperature can't be too high, otherwise, if temperature is more than 350 °C, Si-H and Si-CH₃ of PCS can be reacted with each other. When pressure is further added (for example, 7~8MPa as shown in Fig.3), the infiltration rate for the melted PCS system lowers as temperature is raised.

The infiltrating process conditions of fabricating FRCCMC via melted PCS precursor impregnation pyrolysis method can be given as: infiltration temperature and pressure are 300 °C and 2MPa, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The infiltration rate of the PCS/DVB system is more than that of the melted PCS system at same conditions. The optimum infiltration temperature and pressure of the PCS/DVB solution system and the melted PCS system are 50~60 °C, 2MPa, and 300 °C, 2MPa, respectively.

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